

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine

VOLUME 2
ISSUE 1

JANUARY-MARCH ISSUE
A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume II, Issue I | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

MARDIYA J. BALAHIM, LPT, ED.D

Associate Professor II

Sulu State College

mardiyabalahim69@gmail.com

“WHAT IS LIFE?”

Life is a gift, treasure it.
Life is a calling, answer it.
Life is love, embrace it.
Life is a battlefield, fight it.

Life is an adventure, enjoy it.
Life is a journey, explore it.
Life is a vow, honor it.
Life is a dream, realize it.

Life is a song, sing it.
Life is a struggle, overcome it.
Life is a mountain, climb it.
Life is a fear, conquer it.

Life is a tragedy, face it.
Life is a game, play it.
Life is a moment, seize it.
Life is a masterpiece, behold it.

Life is a goal, accomplish it.
Life is a storm, brave it.
Life is beauty, admire it.
Life is a reality, accept it.

